

Sediment Transport Dynamics in Meander-Affected Straight Channels: Experimental Analysis and Model Development

Madhusmita Behera^{#1}, Abhijit Mangaraj^{*2}, Rajesh Kumar Mantry^{#3}

^{#1}CAPGS, Rourkela ^{*2#3} Department of Civil Engineering, GIFT Autonomous

Abstract— This research investigates the sediment transport dynamics in meander-affected straight channels, focusing on how factors like water depth, sediment particle size, Reynolds number, and Froude number influence sediment transport rates. Using an experimental flume setup with sand of varying grain sizes (0.5 mm to 2 mm), sediment transport rates were measured under controlled conditions. The study explores sediment erosion, deposition patterns, and velocity distribution in both smooth and rough bed channels. Results show that sediment transport is highly sensitive to changes in flow velocity and bed roughness, with higher sediment transport rates observed in rough beds. A mathematical model was developed using regression analysis, considering dimensionless parameters like relative particle size, Reynolds number, and Froude number. The model successfully predicts sediment transport rates and provides a valuable tool for future research on channel dynamics. This study's findings contribute to understanding fluvial processes in modified straight channels and offer insights into sediment management and channel stability in natural and engineered river systems. Future work could extend the model to non-prismatic channels and explore sediment transport using different bed materials and channel configurations.

Keywords— Sediment transport, Meander-affected straight channel, Hydraulic parameters, Froude number, Reynolds number, Particle size, Erosion and deposition.

Introduction

Rivers, one of nature's most dynamic and ever-evolving features, can be broadly classified into three types based on their patterns: straight rivers, meandering rivers, and braided rivers. Each type is characterized by its distinct morphological and flow characteristics, shaped by the underlying terrain, flow velocity, sediment load, and other hydraulic factors. Understanding the sediment transport mechanisms in these rivers is critical for environmental management, flood control, and infrastructure planning.

Sediment transport, the process by which solid particles such as sand, gravel, and boulders are moved by a fluid (water, wind, ice, or mud), plays a pivotal role in shaping river channels. In rivers, this process is driven by the movement of water and its ability to erode, transport, and deposit sediments. This study focuses on sediment transport in a straight channel affected by meandering, exploring the interplay between flow dynamics and sediment movement.

1.1 River Types

1.1.1 Straight River

A straight river refers to a channel where there are minimal or no variations in the path of the flow. Such rivers are often found where the underlying geology or human intervention restricts the natural tendency of water to meander. Straight rivers are typically short, with a length-to-width ratio of 10 to 12 times the channel width. These rivers are rare in nature due to the natural instability and tendency of river channels to meander over time, especially in the absence of external control measures.

1.1.2 Meandering River

A meandering river is characterized by a series of sinuous bends and curves. The meandering nature of these rivers is a result of erosion and deposition processes that occur at different points along the riverbanks. When the water flow velocity increases, the riverbank erodes at certain points, causing the river to change its course gradually. The degree of meandering is often measured by the ratio of the

channel slope to the valley slope, which exceeds 1.5 in meandering rivers. Most rivers exhibit straight segments but transition into meanders as the water's energy shapes the channel over time.

1.1.3 Braided River

Braided rivers are networks of interconnected channels separated by small, temporary islands or bars of sediment. These rivers typically form in environments where the sediment load is high, and the river slope is steep. The large quantity of sediment carried by the river causes frequent deposition, leading to the formation of multiple channels. During low flow periods, the discharge varies significantly, leading to the erosion of banks and the easy deposition of sediments.

1.1.4. Sediment Transport

Sediment transport is a natural and essential process in the development and evolution of river channels. It involves the movement of sediment particles such as sand, gravel, and clay, facilitated by the flow of water, wind, or ice. In river systems, the transport of sediment is primarily driven by the velocity of water. Higher flow velocities lead to increased sediment carrying capacity, resulting in more significant erosion and deposition activities.

There are several factors that contribute to the erosion of riverbanks, including rainfall, runoff, and the type of soil or sediment present in the region. Soil erosion due to rainfall can be classified into four types: splash erosion, rill erosion, sheet erosion, and gully erosion. These processes lead to the detachment and movement of soil particles, which are eventually carried downstream by the flowing water.

Sediment transport in rivers can be categorized into different types based on the mode of transport:

Aeolian: Transport of fine particles by wind.

Fluvial: Transport by water, the most common mode in rivers, which can move large particles due to the density and viscosity of water.

Coastal: Transport influenced by wave and current action near the shore.

Glacial: Sediment transport by glaciers, which can move a wide range of particle sizes.

Hill Slope: Sediment transport in hilly areas due to gravity, land sliding, or animal activity.

Debris Flow: Movement of large sediment particles in a slurry of mud or water.

1.2 Research Objective

The primary objective of this research is to study the variation in sediment transport rates with respect to critical hydraulic parameters such as water depth, particle size, Froude number, and Reynolds number. By conducting experimental analysis, this study aims to develop an understanding of the factors influencing sediment movement in a straight channel affected by meandering.

1.1 Objectives

The primary objective is to formulate the variation of sediment transport rates with respect to water depth, particle size, Froude number, and Reynolds number in meander-affected straight channels. This work aims to fill the gap in existing literature by developing a model that accounts for sediment transport variations in these specific channel types.

2. Methodology

2.1 Experimental Setup

Experiments were conducted in a mild steel flume 12 meters long, 0.33 meters wide, and 0.11 meters deep with a bed slope of 0.001. The channel setup included both smooth and rough beds, using sand particles with sizes ranging from 0.5mm to 2mm. A point gauge was employed to measure water depth at various sections, and volumetric discharge was measured using a vertical manometer and a volumetric tank. Sediment transport rates were calculated by collecting transported sediments at hourly intervals.

Fig 1: Layout of Experimental Setup

Table 2.1 Detailed geometric of the channel

Sl no	Channel type	Straight
1	Main channel width	0.33m
2	Depth of main channel	0.11m
3	Side slope	1:1
4	Top width	0.55m
5	Sediment thickness	0.05m
6	Bed Slope	0.001
7	Time of exp.	30hr
8	Aspect ratio	3
9	Flume size	12m×0.55m×0.11m

Table 2.2 Details of Grain

Sl no	Grain (sand)	Grain Size
1	D_{10}	0.25mm
2	D_{20}	0.4mm
3	D_{30}	0.5mm
4	D_{40}	0.6mm
5	D_{50}	0.75mm
6	D_{60}	0.8mm
7	D_{70}	1mm
8	D_{80}	1.25mm
9	D_{90}	2mm

2.2 Instruments and Apparatus

Key instruments included pitot tubes for velocity measurements, volumetric tanks for discharge measurements, and various sieves to classify sediment size. The experimental flume was equipped with an overhead tank, centrifugal pumps, flow straighteners, and adjustable gates to control flow rates and ensure uniform flow conditions.

Fig 2: Overhead Tank

Fig 3: List of Manometers

Fig 4: fabrication of Channel

2.3 Experimental Procedure

Experiments were conducted over 30 hours to measure sediment transport rates for different flow conditions. Water was allowed to run continuously in the flume until uniform flow was achieved. Sediment transport rates were measured by collecting sediment samples at regular intervals, and velocity measurements were taken using a pitot tube connected to a manometer.

3. Results and Analysis

3.1 Velocity Contours and Profiles

The velocity distribution in both smooth and rough beds was analyzed. In meander-affected straight channels, the highest velocity was observed near the center of the channel, while lower velocities were recorded near the banks. The difference between velocity profiles for smooth and rough beds was significant due to increased friction in rough beds.

Fig5 : Velocity Contour for Smooth Bed (cm/s)

Fig 6 : Velocity Contour for Mobile Bed (cm/sec)

Fig 7: Longitudinal Velocity Profile at various points.

Table 3.1 Comparing data with other approaches

Time(hr.)	Measured bed load rate (kg/sec)	Computed bed load rate (kg./sec)using the models of		
		Einstein(1950)	Shields(1936)	MPM(1948)
1	0.003	0.0396	0.008	0.029
2	0.002	0.469	0.005	0.034
3	0.003	0.224	0.004	0.037
4	0.002	0.113	0.003	0.040
5	0.003	0.284	0.002	0.043
6	0.004	0.553	0.002	0.044
7	0.004	0.035	0.001	0.048
8	0.005	0.009	0.001	0.052
9	0.005	0.007	0.008	0.060

Fig 8: Observed vs. Predicted data with different approach

3.2 Sediment Transport Rates

Experimental results revealed that sediment transport rates are directly proportional to flow discharge. Higher discharges resulted in increased sediment transport rates, particularly in rough channels. The sediment transport process in meander-affected straight channels was found to be influenced by hydraulic parameters such as Froude number and Reynolds number, as well as particle size.

3.3 Regression Analysis

Regression analysis was performed to develop a predictive model for sediment transport rates. The best-fit model was based on three dimensionless parameters: relative particle size (D/h), Froude number (Fr), and Reynolds number (Re). The regression model equation was derived as follows:

$$\frac{Q_s}{q} = 0.0034 - 0.1937 \left(\frac{D}{h} \right) + 0.0001Fr + 0.7075Re$$

Where:

Q_s = sediment transport rate,

q = discharge,

D = particle size,

h = water depth,

Fr = Froude number,

Re = Reynolds number.

Fig 9: Linear regression

4. Discussion

4.1 Comparison with Existing Models

The derived model was compared with well-established sediment transport models, including the Einstein (1950), Shields (1936), and Meyer-Peter and Müller (1948) approaches. Among these, the Shields approach yielded the closest match with experimental data for meander-affected straight channels. The comparison validated the proposed model's accuracy in predicting sediment transport rates.

Fig 10 . Actual value Vs. Predicted value of different models.

Table 4.1 : Comparison of different models

Time (hr)	Measured Bed Load Rate (kg/s)	Einstein Model (1950)	Shields Model (1936)	MPM Model (1948)
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3	0.003	0.224	0.004	0.037
4	0.002	0.113	0.003	0.040
5	0.003	0.284	0.002	0.043

4.2 Theoretical Insights

The relationship between sediment transport rates and hydraulic parameters such as Froude number, Reynolds number, and particle size was further explored. The study found that sediment transport is more efficient in meander-affected straight channels due to increased turbulence and flow variability. The presence of meanders disrupts the uniformity of sediment deposition and erosion patterns, leading to higher sediment transport rates compared to straight channels.

4.3 Limitations

The study is limited to specific Reynolds and Froude number ranges ($Re = 29,457$ to $587,795$, $Fr = 0.04$ to 0.15). Further research is needed to extend the model to higher flow regimes and different sediment types. The experiments were conducted with sand particles only, which may limit the generalizability of the model to other sediment types, such as gravel or silt.

5. Conclusion and Future Work

5.1 Conclusion

This study successfully developed a regression-based model to predict sediment transport rates in meander-affected straight channels. The model incorporates dimensionless parameters such as relative particle size, Froude number, and Reynolds number, and shows strong agreement with experimental data. Key findings include the significant impact of channel geometry and flow discharge on sediment transport rates.

5.2 Future Scope

Future research should focus on expanding the model to different channel types and sediment materials, such as gravel and silt. Further experimentation with varying bed slopes and channel widths would help refine the model. Additionally, investigating the impact of vegetation and other environmental factors on sediment transport in meandering channels would provide a more comprehensive understanding of fluvial processes.

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